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02

Awareness about the Usage and Academic Procreation for Social Media Among Student - Teachers

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Abstract: This study examines the awareness of Social Media s usages and academic among student teachers in Solapur District, Maharashtra, India. A descriptive survey method was employed, and data were collected from 237 student teachers using a Simple random sampling technique in Solapur District. Social Media Usage and academic Procreation Awareness Inventory which is constructed and standardized by Tuckman Procrastination Scale (TPS) & scale Social Media Addiction Scale Student Form (SMAS SF) was used to collect the data. This study found that Majority of student teachers in Solapur District had a moderate level of awareness in using social media and Academic Procreation. This study sheds light on the need for teacher-training colleges to incorporate social media literacy programs into their curriculum. This would help prospective teachers develop the necessary skills for responsible and effective use of social media in educational settings.

Key Words: Social media, academic procreation, awareness, student- teachers etc

Introduction:

Social media is the most prominent way

of communication and it is emerging very quickly in the contemporary scenario. It is the form of media that allow people to communicate and share information using internet and mobile phones. Social media is internet-based technology, which facilitates the sharing of ideas, thoughts and information and are normally dedicated to forums, microblogging, social networking, social bookmarking, social curation, and wikis. Users engage with social media via computer, tablet or smartphone via web-based software or web application, often utilizing it for messaging. Social media plays a crucial role on the way people engage with the world around them. Younger generation all over the world are the core consumers of social media and it is closely knitted to their day-to-day life in abundance of ways. Research works in this field aims to understand the impact of social media in the physical, psychological, social, and emotional characteristics of human beings and encourage us to think about how can we mitigate any potential harms hence to utilize this technology in a healthy and effective way.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The researcher has made attempts to study previous research works conducted on Influence of social media usage among adolescence self-esteem and academic procrastination. The review of literature gives an insight into the studies conducted earlier in these areas.

Alyssa Saiphoo (2019) of Ryerson University, Toronto conducted a study regarding "The relationship between social media use and self-esteem". The study found a small, significant, negative relationship between social network sites use and self-esteem, suggesting that higher level of social network sites users is associated with lower level of self-esteem.

Liyaqat Bashir (2019) conducted a study in "Social networking usage, Academic procrastination and performance among university students: role of self-efficacy and metacognitive

beliefs". The study revealed that self-efficacy and metacognitive beliefs mediates the relationship of social networking usage with academic procrastination and performance

Lenhart (2015) Pew research center indicates that 71% of 13 to 17 years old use Facebook, 52% use Instagram, and 41% use Snapchat in 2015. Teenage girls are also using image-based social media platforms more frequently than their male counterparts; 61% of girls use Instagram versus 44% of boys.

Kwaah (2024) revealed that WhatsApp was more popular among male teachers and Facebook was more popular among the female teachers in Ghana.

Amutha and Kennedy (2015) observed that female student teachers had better social media usage than male student teachers. The findings from various studies on social media usage among student teachers across different regions and demographics indicate that awareness and usage patterns differ among districts and educational institutions. Factors such as study year, gender, and institutional type influence social media behaviour. Therefore, the investigator made the decision to carry out this investigation.

Operational Definition:

1. Social media: social media is a computer-based technology that facilitate the sharing of ideas, thoughts, and information through the building of virtual networks and communities.

2. Procrastination: Procrastination comes from the Latin pro, meaning "forward, forth, or in favour of," and crustiness, meaning "of tomorrow". Procrastination is defined as the act off or delaying an action to a later time (Bachrach, 2012).

Objectives:

1. To identify the level of social media usage awareness among the student teachers.
2. To find out whether there is any significant difference in the awareness of social media usage among the student teachers based on

gender, locality, age, educational qualification.
3. To study the relationship between social media usage and academic procrastination in student-teachers.

Hypotheses of the study

1. There is no significant difference in the awareness of social media usage among the student teachers based on gender.
2. There is no significant difference in the awareness of social media usage among the student teachers based on locality.
3. There is no significant difference in the awareness of social media usage among the student teachers based on age.
4. There is no significant difference in the awareness of social media usage among the student teachers based on educational qualification.

Research Method & Design:

Method: The investigator adopted descriptive survey method for determining the awareness of social media usage among the student teachers.

Design: In the present study, a co-relational research design is used to study the relationship between social media usage and academic procrastination among students pursuing higher education.

Population and Sample:

Student teachers who were studying Bachelor of Education course in Maharashtra P. A. H. Solapur University, Solapur affiliated self-financing colleges in Solapur district considered as population of this study. A total of 237 student teachers were selected by using simple random sampling technique.

Tool Used for the Study:

1. Tuckman Procrastination Scale (TPS) developed a Social Media Usage Awareness scale, which the investigator used. This scale has 16 statements about the awareness of social media usage, to which respondents can provide responses. One of Tuckman's major goals was to develop an easily adaptable self-report in-

strument which identifies academic procrastinators. He performed a factor analysis and identified a reliable (Cronbach's alpha = .86) 16-item scale from an original item pool of 72 items. However, Tuckman's first factor analysis consisted of a sample size of 50 participants, which is cause for considerable concern according to Tabachnick and Fidell (2007).

2. Social Media Addiction Scale Student Form (SMAS SF)

Social media addiction scale students form developed by Cengiz Sahin (2018). This is a 5-point Likert type scale which consists of 29 items and 4 sub-dimensions. 1-5 items are within virtual tolerance sub dimension; 6-14 items are within virtual communication sub dimension; 15-23 items are under virtual problem sub dimension and 24-29 items are under virtual information sub dimension. All the items in the scale are positive. The highest point that can be scored from the scale is 145, and the least one is 29. The higher scores indicate that agent perceives himself as a "social media addict."

Statistical techniques used

The investigator applied percentage analysis, student 't' test, One-way ANOVA for processing the data

Table No 1.1

Levels of social media awareness among the students – teachers

Level	Score range	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Low	0 - 6	0	0
Moderate	7 - 12	127	53.58
High	13 - 20	110	46.41

According to Table 1.1 46.41% of student teachers use social media with a high level of awareness, while 53.28% use social media with a moderate level of awareness. The analysis suggests that most student teachers from the selected sample in Solapur District had a moderate level of awareness regarding their usage of

social media.

Table No 1.2

Levels of social media awareness among the students - teachers based on gender

Variables	Sub Variables	N	Mean	S. D.	t value	Significance at 0.05 level
Gender	Male	70	7.38	1.87	2.72	Significant
	Female	167	13.22	2.12		

Table 1.2 shows that the calculated t value 2.72 is higher than the table value 1.76 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis 1 is rejected. Hence, there is a significant difference in the awareness of social media usage among the student teachers based on gender. Female student teachers showed better awareness in social media usage than the male student teachers.

Table No 1.3

Levels of social media awareness among the students - teachers based on locality

Variables	Sub Variables	N	Mean	S. D.	t value	Significance at 0.05 level
Locality	Rural	107	11.94	2.22	0.27	Not Significant
	Urban	130	13.22	2.62		

The data shown in Table 1.3 indicates that the calculated t value of 0.27 is less than the critical table value of 1.6 at a significance level of 0.05. Therefore, the investigator fails to reject the null hypothesis 3. Hence, there is no significant difference in the awareness of social media usage among the student teachers based on locality.

Table No 1.3

Levels of social media awareness among the students - teachers based on age

Variables	Sub Variables	S. S	df	M. S	f value	Significance at 0.05 level
Age	Below 25	15.10	2	7.55	1.39	Not Significant
	23 - 30	1050.00	210	5.27		
	Above 30	1155.71	105.71			

Table 1.4 indicates that the calculated F value of 1.39 is less than the critical table value of 3.00 at a significance level of 0.05. Therefore, the investigator fails to reject null hypothesis 3. Thus, there is no significant difference in the awareness of social media usage among the student teachers based on age.

3. Thus, there is no significant difference in the awareness of social media usage among the student teachers based on age.

Table 1.5

Social Media Usage Awareness of student teachers based on educational qualification

Variables	Sub Variables	N	Mean	S. D.	t value	Significance at 0.05 level
Educational qualification	UG	170	10.70	2.00	0.7	Not Significant
	PG	67	7.23	1.79		

The data shown in Table 1.5 shows that the calculated t value 0.7 is less than the critical table value of 1.9 at a significance level of 0.05. Therefore, the investigator fails to reject null hypothesis 4. Hence, there is no significant difference in the awareness of social media usage among the student teachers based on educational qualification.

Table 2.1: Correlation Among Social Media Usage and Academic Procrastination Among Students Pursuing Higher Education

Variables	N	Correlation	Significance
Social Media Usage	237	0.189**	**p<0.01
Academic Procrastination			

****Significant at 0.01 level**

The statistical outcome in table 3 shows the coefficient of correlation between academic procrastination and social media usage of women's students pursuing higher education. Examination of the correlation matrix reveals that social media usage has the highest correlation with the academic procrastination ($r=0.189^{**}$, $p<0.01$). So, it reveals that significant correlation is found between social media usage with academic procrastination among students pursuing higher education. Thus, the hypothesis stated that there is a significant relationship between social media usage and academic procrastination among students pursuing higher education is accepted. Thus, there exists significant positive relationship between social media usage with academic procrastination among students pursuing higher education.

Thus, it can be interpreted that excess use of social media usage increases students' academic procrastination.

Discussion:

This study found that most student teachers in Solapur District had a moderate level of awareness regarding their usage of social media. This study agrees with the findings of Turkmans who discovered that most student teachers in the Erode District possess a moderate level of awareness regarding their usage of social media. This could be attributed to the careless mindset and insufficient knowledge of student teachers regarding the proper usage of social media.

The investigator discovered that female student teachers had better awareness than male student teachers in using social media properly.

This study revealed that student teachers residing in the hostel had a higher level of awareness regarding social media usage compared to student teachers who are day scholars.

Conclusion:

This study shows that most student teachers in Solapur District have a moderate level of awareness regarding their use of social media. The demographic factors of gender and residence have a significant influence on the use of social media among student teachers. These findings indicate that there is a requirement for specific training programmes aimed at improving social media literacy. Additional variables that influence student instructors' awareness and utilisation of social media could be the subject of future research.

After analysing the relationship of social networking usage with academic procrastination among college women students, the results revealed that there exists a statistically significant relationship between social networking usage and academic procrastination.

Recommendation for Feature Research:

· The study of various social media portals had

been conducted in a general manner as it can also be conducted portal wise e.g. Impact of Facebook, impact of twitter & so on.

· The present study is done only to the teenagers, similar study can be conducted to school and under-graduate students.

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